

Can Bangladesh go green?

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Abstract

Gradual environmental degradation, climate change and diminishing natural resources created extra pressure to adopt an unconventional approach to support export-driven economic activities. “Our common future—Call for action” concept developed by Brundtland has laid the founding stone of going green. As an overpopulated country, Bangladesh encounters various environmental degradation. The study aimed to identify the challenges Bangladesh faces to go green. It was found that depletion of natural resources, climate change, industrial pollution, traditional waste management, brackish shrimp culture, lack of environmental justice, lack 3R technologies, traditional brick kiln, lack of industrial ecology, greenwashing, lack of public awareness and insufficient green energy are the main challenges to go green. The study recommended several solutions to overcome the bottlenecks.

Keywords: Go green, greenwashing, 3R, industrial ecology, green energy, the tragedy of commons, environmental justice

Introduction

The “Tragedy of the Commons” described overconsumption and depletion of resources (Ostrom 2008; Hardin 1998). On the other hand, the concept of sustainability emerged from the “Our common future—Call for action” concept developed by Brundtland (1987). In that concept, it is apprehended that the world faces unforeseen changes that occur in the environment. Sustainability was endorsed by the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development held in Rio de Janeiro in 1992, and reaffirmed by the World Summit on Sustainable Development held in Johannesburg in 2002 (Borowy 2013; Telfer 2012; Gerasimova 2017; Smith *et al.* 2010; Palmer 1992).

The Asia and Pacific region has become the frontier of the 21st century in shaping the world economy (Dicken 2003; Mathews 2006). The economic growth is driven primarily by exports which have led to expanded production requirements needed to fuel an ever-increasing amount of trade. This has accelerated the environmental degradation of many countries in this region (UNEP 2011; Rice 2009). Gradual environmental degradation, climate change and diminishing natural resources created extra pressure to adopt an unconventional approach to support the export-driven economic activities of this region (Gonzalez 2015; Shahzad *et al.* 2021). The past axiom of “grow first, clean up later” cannot run more in a region which has limited natural resources and a rapidly growing population directly dependent on natural resources. These countries are now shouldering an increasingly greater share of regional and global environmental production-related burdens (Rock & Angel 2007).

The fifth Ministerial Conference on “Environment and Development in Asia and the Pacific” embraced the approach of environmentally sound Green Growth (Jabeen & Khan 2022; Kwon 2010; Chung & Quah 2010). The Conference endorsed Green Growth as a policy and a powerful strategy to promote “win-win” approaches to reconciling the conflict between current pathways for the achievement of two important Millennium Development Goal-1 and 7 (Guo *et al.* 2018; Bina 2013; Wanner 2015). Green Growth emphasizes demand-side management and promotes environmentally sustainable decisions through the market, economic and fiscal systems (Ming *et al.* 2013; Sahin *et al.* 2019; Yang *et al.* 2022). It addresses public awareness of environmentally sound governance and the development and deployment of new environmentally improved

technologies (Sarkar 2013; Popp 2012; Dogaru 2021). On the other hand, the Rio+20 summit in 2012 generated a parallel concept to the MDGs, which are widely known as Sustainable Development Goals (Sachs 2015; Loewe 2012). SDG-12 focuses on efficient use of resources, cleaner production, responsible consumption, 3R (reuse, reduce and recycle), and minimum pollution and waste generation (Guo *et al.* 2020; Belmonte-Ureña *et al.* 2021). Energy and material productivity improvements were mainly driven by structural changes in the economy in Bangladesh, which is a transition from agricultural to service-based economies. Yet these are found to be insufficient to deliver green growth (Baniya *et al.* 2021). The study aimed to identify the challenges Bangladesh faces to go green.

Methodology

Empirical data was used for this study. Five focus group discussions were done incorporating the respondents from diverse stakeholders like economists, environmentalists, local governments, community leaders, foresters and industrialists. A total number of 10 key respondents were interviewed to find out the solutions. Content analysis was done to interpret the data.

How far Bangladesh is?

Environmental degradation and depletion of natural resources

The respondents opined that environmental degradation and depletion of natural resources in Bangladesh occur faster than in the past decades due to poverty, over-population and lack of awareness about environmental protection. It is manifested by deforestation, destruction of wetlands, depletion of soil nutrients, etc. Due to high population density and sharply skewed distribution of lands, the forest resources are overexploited (Rahman 2022 a, b; Rahman *et al.* 2009, Rahman & Vacik 2009). Per capita forestland in the country is around 0.02 ha and the existing natural forests are decreasing at an alarming rate (Rahman 2023 a, b).

Industrial pollution and waste management

According to respondents' perceptions, the rapid growth of urbanization and industrialization are increasing environmental pollution. The river and marine ecosystems are now facing an onslaught of pollution because of the increased level of waste discharges from various sources.

Major sources are domestic sewage, tourist waste, industrial waste, commercial waste, agricultural waste, institutional waste, street sweepings, construction debris, mining activities and sanitation residues etc. They added that solid waste pollution, heavy metal pollution, organochlorine pesticides pollution and oil pollution along the rivers and coastal areas are jeopardizing the scenarios. Bhuyan & Islam (2017) reported that oil pollution adversely affects estuarine biota.

Climate change

The respondents noted that natural calamities like floods, cyclones and tidal surges result in severe socio-economic and environmental damage. Climate change will affect all human and ecological systems and socio-economic development activities (Ahmed *et al.* 1999). Hickel & Kallis (2020) argued that green growth cannot be achieved by decoupling from carbon emissions. Brackish water from the Bay of Bengal is invading the freshwater bodies of the coastal areas of Bangladesh (Rahman 2023c). However, climate change has recently been identified to threaten the sustainability of coastal aquaculture (Ahmed & Glaser 2016; Ahmed 2013; Ahmed *et al.* 2019, Rahman 2023 f, g).

Brackish shrimp culture

The respondents pointed out that brackish shrimp culture has brought widespread social and economic benefits in exchange for environmental degradation. The expansion of shrimp farming resulted in decreases in crop production and many environmental problems in the form of a shortage of livestock fodder, fuel scarcity and decreases in traditional labour forces (Karim 2006). Rahman (2020) reported that the brackish culture has increased salination in the mangrove areas. The Sundari, the pioneer tree species of the Sundarbans mangrove suffers from the 'Top dyeing' disease with the increase of salinity. Salinity increases the tree mortality rate by reducing the production of new leaves, leaf longevity and the leaf area (Rahman 2023f).

Brick kiln

The respondents opined that the number of brick kiln is rising day by day, which harm soils. Hazardous elements, toxicity, non-biodegradable elements, and trace metals originating from the kiln are threatening the environment. Hossain *et al.* (2019) reported that the brick kiln of the

country poses a great to natural ecosystems. The pollution from brick kiln clusters in Greater Dhaka (Guttikunda *et al.* 2013, Rahman 2023h).

Insufficient renewable energy

The respondents argued that the renewable energy sector is unable to contribute to energy sufficiency. Nowadays, Bangladesh shares a percentage of renewable energy only 3% of the total energy ratio (Uddin *et al.* 2019). The agricultural sector mostly uses diesel to cover its energy needs, with diesel accounting for 90% of the total energy demand (Sapkota *et al.* 2021). The coal-based energy is increasing in the country (Das *et al.* 2020).

Lack of 3R (Reuse, renew and recycle)

The respondents opined that the 3R concept in Bangladesh has not been flourished and well-practised. The adoption of 3R technology in waste management in the city can ensure zero waste (Ahmed *et al.* 2023). Treating waste as a resource is the first step towards sustainable waste management and conserving resources (Visvanathan *et al.* 2007).

Lack of industrial ecology

The respondents noted the implantation of the industrial ecology concept in the industry sector is absent and unknown, though it has high potential in the sugar mills. The waste of sugar mills can be used in paper and liquor manufacturing. Consequently, more products can be manufactured by using a single raw material which will lead to zero waste and maximum utilization of natural resources.

Greenwashing

Based on the respondents' perceptions greenwashing occurs in food, beverage, cosmetics, medicine, brickfield, tourism and transportation sectors very often. Rahman (2023d) reported that eco-tourism run by travel agencies, tour operators, hotels, motels and resorts is a quick and superficially "green" visit within a conventional package.

Lack of environmental justice

The respondents highlighted that lack of environmental justice is one of the major causes of environmental justice. Rahman (2021a, b) revealed that ordinary people could not seek justice

from the court directly for environmental damage due to bubbles in the legal and policy framework.

Lack of awareness

The respondents added that most people are not aware of going green and green growth. Umar & Khamidi (2012) showed that a lack of public awareness is a major obstacle to achieving green growth. Rahman (2023e) reported that going green should start from the birth of an infant.

What to do?

Increasing carbon sinks through plantations

- Preparing a master plan to expand carbon sinks and enhance the economic value of forest resources
- Forestation in fallow land to create new carbon sinks
- Reducing the heat island effect through urban forestation

Green energy

- Emphasis should be given to increasing the proportion of renewable energy in the national electricity grid
- Extending the use of biogas produced from the organic waste
- Adopting 3Rs Model (recycle, reduce, reuse) and formulating the resource-saving society
- Social movements
- Initiating a forest carbon cycle village (biomass green town) as a low-carbon society model
- Building up regional Green Hub
- Promoting a cooperative system for response to climate change with the community
- Promoting a 'Green Practice Agreement' with the community
- Demonstrating a 'forest love movement'

Green governance

- Emphasizing eco-production and eco-economic planning
- Imposing Green Tax on environmentally non-friendly products and services
- Promoting environmentally friendly goods and services
- Promoting industrial ecology concepts
- Investing more in natural capital
- Ensuring environmental justice for all

- Emphasizing cleaner production and responsible consumption
- Forming a recycling society

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